

CULTIVATING RESILIENCE: THE COPING STRATEGIES OF TEACHERS IN HANDLING MULTI-GRADE CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

Multi-grade teaching is a strategy to expand access to education, particularly in remote areas. However, it presents challenges for teachers. This study explored the coping mechanisms employed by teachers handling multi-grade classes. Additionally, descriptive-correlation design was used. The study described teacher profiles (age, sex, education, etc.) and their attitudes towards multi-grade classes. It then investigated correlations between these profiles, the challenges encountered, and the coping mechanisms used. The findings revealed that teachers with higher educational attainment, relevant training, and positive attitudes towards multi-grade classes employed more effective coping mechanisms. The grade level taught was the only significant profile variable related to challenges faced. Also, a moderate, statistically significant correlation emerged between coping mechanisms and the challenges encountered. This suggests that teachers utilize their coping strategies based on the specific challenges they face in their multi-grade classrooms. In conclusion, teacher profiles, particularly educational attainment, training, and attitude, influence coping mechanisms in multi-grade settings. The challenges encountered also play a role, with teachers adapting their strategies accordingly.

Keywords: *Multi-grade Curriculum, Coping Mechanism, Adaptation, Multi-grade Teaching, Elementary Teachers, Multi-grade Teachers, Multi-grade Learners, Curriculum Management and Organization, Classroom Management Strategies, Methodological Aspects, Material resources, and Time Management*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, people's access to education is highly prioritized, as it is considered a right for every citizen. With that, learning opportunities become more available for students who were unable to grasp learning before. Also, through the Education for All (EFA) program, all students are entitled to learning that respects diversity.

According to Operti and Zhang (2014), inclusive education supports high-quality and equitable education for all. With that, compulsory education is emphasized, which aims to give all citizens a fair start in life and equal opportunities as adults (Joyce, 2014). However, many countries in the Asia–Pacific region have millions of people living in scattered, thinly populated highlands, mountainous regions, and on small islands, which makes it difficult to provide high-quality education, particularly a high-quality primary education (Buaraphan, et al. 2018).

Therefore, Joyce (2014) highlighted the fact that multi-grade education is understood to be a practical option for expanding access to basic education for disadvantaged children, especially those living in rural areas. As emphasized by Taole (2014), multi-grade teaching schools is an important policy option for providing access to education for learners in remote areas. Thus, as a result of global focus on equality of education for students, especially in remote and thinly populated areas, multigrade teaching is predominant and is increasing (Shareefa, 2021).

Moreover, Kalender and Erdem (2021) emphasized that there are many reasons that make Multigrade Classroom Implementation (MCI) compulsory. Some of the most common reasons worldwide are dispersed settlement, social and economic conditions, difficulty in transportation and geographical features. While according to Dogan, et al. (2020), the common reasons for having multigrade classes are insufficient number of students, geographic or economic status and insufficient number of teachers for each grade.

In the Philippines, following Republic Act 9155, or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, education has been made free and compulsory for all Filipino children (Msimanga, 2019). Thus, the Department of Education (DepEd) mandates the establishment of complete elementary schools in every barangay forming multigrade classes in some remote barangays (Naparan & Alinsug, 2021).

Additionally, Ramrathan and Mzimela (2016) highlighted that the concept multi-grade teaching is described in different ways such as multi-groups or multi-class or combination group teaching. Aside from that, according to Taole (2022), other terminologies of multi-grade teaching are multi-age, multi-stage, mixed grade, mixed classes, multi classes. Engin (2018) underlined that multigrade teaching is a practice in which students from different age, skill and class level continue their education and training together in the same class.

Furthermore, multigrade classrooms play effective roles because it enables the children living in rural and distant places to access education as a right since the most important reason for the presence of multigrade classroom is the scarcity of the students in rural areas (Karaçoban & Karakuş, 2022). With that, according to Khazaei et al. (2016), the main reason for organizing multi-grade classrooms is that the number of students of one grade is less than the minimum number of students determined for formally holding a classroom.

According to Çakir and Firat (2022), the advantages of multigrade classrooms are: students in multi grade classrooms are able to develop important skills such as study skills, self-learning, managing their own studies and conducting research, offer individual development chances to students on subjects they are interested in and talented in, offer students a chance of individual development in the subjects they are interested in and receive education in line with their individual differences, students in higher grades are also able to review their previous knowledge while coaching students in lower grades, and students are able to develop their socialization skills and emotional skills better.

Correspondingly, according to Taole (2020), diversity is also a factor to consider in teaching contexts at multigrade classes. In a multigrade classroom, learners have very different learning needs because of the range of ages and backgrounds in the class. Thus, teachers need to know how to differentiate student learning activities to cater for this range of needs (Bannister-Tyrrell & Pringle, 2021). In that manner, multigrade teaching can be seen as challenging because of the requirement to differentiate class material and activities to cater for children of different ages and stages (Quail & Smyth, 2014). Aside from this challenge of differentiation, in Africa, Turkey and Netherlands, multigrade teachers experience challenges such as transportation, illiteracy of parents, poor economic backgrounds, excessive effort of the teacher, lack of time, language problems and teacher challenges in the actual teaching and learning process.

In addition, in the study entitled “Instructional leadership in multi-grade classrooms: What can mono-grade teachers learn from their resilience?”, the findings show that teachers were faced with challenges including lack of proper training, insufficient support from stakeholders, not any workshops organized for multi-grade teachers and lack of resources at school (Ramrathan & Ngubane, 2013). Consequently, Engin (2018) revealed that the difficulties encountered by classroom teachers in multigrade teaching are excessive effort of the teacher, high expectations from the student, lack of time, difficulty in reaching the aims, non-teaching roles, not being supported, lack of education, physical conditions, and language problems.

Also, curricula across the globe are not structured for multi-grade teaching. Thus, drawing from the accounts of multi-grade teaching, especially in rural contexts, teachers teaching in these situations have to rely on their teacher agency to make decisions on teaching strategies, lesson context, lesson activities and teaching and learning resources to make some impact on learning (Ramrathan & Mzimela, 2016).

Therefore, the applications of multi-grade classes have certain limits such as lack

of application, sourcing, learning and teaching materials in the schools, few support of parents, negative perspective of education, the negative influence of limited village life on the professionalism and social life of teachers. Correspondingly, classroom management, appropriate methods, finding techniques and creating learning spheres are difficulties that appear in multigrade classes (Çiftçi & Baykan, 2013). With that, it can be settled that teachers are faced with multiple challenges for teaching in multi-grade classrooms (Ramrathan & Ngubane, 2013).

As according to Çakir and Firat (2022), the disadvantages of multi grade classrooms are: class preparations are very time-consuming and not all teachers are equipped with the necessary skills and experience to teach in multi grade classrooms. Phajane (2014) emphasized that many teachers lack the knowledge and skills to manage multi-grade classes effectively as they have been trained for single-grade teaching.

Hence, as highlighted by Taole (2014), achieving excellence in teaching and learning in rural contexts, with the application of multigrade classes, remains a challenge for teachers and other sectors of the educational change endeavors. Nevertheless, Naparan and Alinsug (2021) highlighted that despite those limitations and challenges experienced by both teachers and pupils in multigrade school, students strived hard and tried their best to be meaningful and productive, and teachers employ several techniques and strategies to enhance the learners' abilities and skills. According to Naparan and Castaneda (2021), there are coping strategies or mechanisms employed by teachers in handling multi-grade classes such as strengthening one's faith through prayer, using the internet's power and the wealth of information, keeping to a schedule when performing duties and responsibilities, and renewing one's mind through the process of self-conditioning.

Furthermore, in the Philippines, there are 8,379 multigrade schools out of the 38,911 public schools (CNU, 2019). This number can be reasoned out with the data from the Philippine Statistics Authority, which states that the rural population, or those who lived in barangays classified as rural in 2020, comprised 50.10 million persons, or 46.0 percent of the total population in the country.

However, in the rural and remote areas of the Philippines, lack of training and insufficient resources and findings continue to be a teachers' problems in elementary schools (Naparan & Alinsug, 2021).

Moreover, aside from the lack of training for multigrade teachers, Naparan and Alinsug (2021) emphasized that teachers also complain of a lack of sufficient time for handling and managing multi-grade classes and recording the outputs of the learners for the multiple grade levels handled.

Thus, with all the data presented above, the researcher was encouraged to conduct this study. This study primarily aimed to determine the coping strategies employed by teachers in handling multi-grade classes. This study was conducted in rural elementary schools in a province in Eastern Visayas, Philippines.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the coping strategies employed by teachers handling multi-grade classes. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of the following personal variates:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2 civil status;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 years of teaching in multi-grade class;
 - 1.5 grade levels taught;
 - 1.6 number of learners per grade level;
 - 1.7 relevant in-service trainings;
 - 1.8 attitude toward multi-grade classes?

2. What are the coping strategies employed by the teacher-respondents in handling multi-grade classes in terms of:
 - 2.1 Curriculum Management and Organization;
 - 2.2 Classroom Management Strategies;
 - 2.3 Methodological aspects;
 - 2.4 Material resources;
 - 2.5 Time management?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the coping strategies employed by the teacher-respondents in handling multi-grade classes and their profile variates?

4. What are the challenges encountered by the teacher-respondents in handling multi-grade classes in terms of:
 - 4.1 Curriculum Management and Organization;
 - 4.2 Classroom Management Strategies;
 - 4.3 Methodological aspects;
 - 4.4 Material resources;
 - 4.5 Time management?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the teacher-respondents in handling multi-grade classes and their profile variates?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the teacher-respondents in handling multi-grade classes and their coping strategies employed?

7. What interventions maybe derived based on the findings of this study?

METHODOLOGY

This research explored the coping mechanisms used by teachers in handling multi-grade classes in elementary schools. The study employed a quantitative approach with a descriptive-correlation design. Data was collected from 108 teachers in two districts using purposive sampling. A questionnaire with various sections was used to gather information on teacher profiles, attitudes towards multi-grade classes, challenges faced, and coping strategies. The questionnaire's validity was ensured through expert review and a test-retest method. To collect data, researchers obtained permission from school authorities and informed teachers about the study's objectives. Teacher participation was voluntary, and anonymity was offered. Questionnaires were administered to gain relevant information. Data analysis involved statistical tools like frequency counts, percentages, and various correlation coefficients. Software like Microsoft Excel and SPSS were used to analyze the data. The researchers sought to identify relationships between teacher profiles, the challenges they encountered, and the coping mechanisms they employed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. The majority of teachers are young (27-31 years old) and female. This suggests a youthful and predominantly female teaching force in the sample.
2. Most teachers are married (51.85%) but single teachers represent a still substantial portion of the respondents (48.15%). This could be correlated with the young age or influenced by the demands of the profession.
3. The majority of the teachers fall within the Master's Degree Unit Earner category. This can be linked to the ranking and promotion processes of teachers, wherein level of education is part of the criteria.
4. There was a split between relatively newer teachers (<10 years' experience) and those with longer tenure. Notably, teachers are absent with 16-20 years of experience.
5. The majority of teacher-respondents handle two grade levels: Grade 5 and Grade 6 learners (20.37%). However, it was revealed that there are teachers who are handling three classes.
6. The majority of teacher-respondents have 11 to 15 learners. This distribution reflects its alignment with DepED Order. No. 96, s. 1997 on the policies and guidelines in the organization and operation of multi-grade classes, as it was clearly stated in this policy guideline that a maximum of 35 pupils per multi-grade class shall be observed.
7. District and school-level in-service training is most common. National and

- regional training is reported as less frequent.
8. Teacher-respondents have a generally positive attitude toward multi-grade classes. It was revealed that they enjoy dealing with pupils in the multi-grade classrooms.
 9. The statements with the highest weighted means, suggesting the most frequent utilized coping mechanism along Curriculum Management and Organization are: "Provide a good sequence of topics to suit classroom and learners' levels of learning" (4.54) and "Design a classroom activity starting from an easy level and going to a more complex one" (4.51).
 10. The statements with the highest weighted means, suggesting the most frequent utilized coping mechanism along classroom management strategies are: "Establish verbal and nonverbal communication in the classroom" (4.38), "Provide students' flexible grouping in multi-grade classroom" (4.29), and "Learners' individual and group work is on display so they can see the value of their efforts" (4.07).
 11. The statements with the highest weighted means, suggesting the most frequent utilized coping mechanism along Methodological Aspects are: "I take into account the learning styles and the type of intelligence of the students" (4.81) and "I design engaging activities, direct and indirect, that permanently capture the interest of students" (4.56).
 12. The statement with the highest weighted mean, suggesting the most common utilized coping mechanism along Material Resources is "There is sufficient school and learning facilities for conducting lessons in good condition" (3.20).
 13. The statement with the highest weighted means, suggesting the most frequent utilized coping mechanism along time management are: "I teach by grouping learners to maximize time for lesson discussion and activity" (4.36), "I craft the daily lesson log per learning area on time or in advance" (4.00), and "I prepare learning and instructional material a week before you discuss the lesson" (3.76).
 14. The variables that have a significant correlation with teachers' coping mechanisms are: highest educational attainment (weak correlation), relevant in-service training (weak), and attitude toward multi-grade classes.
 15. The correlation between the variable highest educational attainment of teachers and their coping mechanisms suggests that teachers with higher educational levels tend to use more coping mechanisms to adjust to handling multi-grade classes. Also, the correlation between the variable attitude of teachers toward multi-grade classes and their coping mechanisms indicates that teachers who have a positive outlook towards multi-grade classes tend to

- utilize more coping and adaptation mechanisms in handling multi-grade classes. Moreover, the variable relevant in-service training and their coping mechanisms indicates that teachers who have more trainings attended tend to use more coping or adaptation techniques in teaching.
16. The statements with the highest weighted means, suggesting curriculum management and organization as highly challenging are: “The crafting of questions for assessment purposes for multi-group learners is difficult” (3.56) and “The topics discussed with multi-grade learners are of varying complexity” (3.51).
 17. The statements with the highest weighted means, suggesting classroom management strategies as highly challenging situations, are: “Unavailability of technologies such as computers and other gadgets” (3.67), “A noisy environment cannot be avoided during multi-grade classes” (3.62), and “Providing flexible grouping in a multi-grade classroom is hard to achieve” (3.57).
 18. The statements with the highest weighted means, suggesting methodological aspects as highly challenging are: “Lack of relevant training about multi-grade teaching” (3.71), “Submission of weekly design or plan of the multi-grade activities” (3.65), and “Switching the lesson activity from a direct activity of one class to an indirect activity of the other class” (3.63).
 19. The statements with the highest weighted means, suggesting material resources as highly challenging are: “There are no computers available in each classroom or for each teacher” (3.74), “There is no accessible Internet connection” (3.73), “Lack of resources such as learning materials, equipment, and facilities” (3.70), and “There is no functional library within the school” (3.57).
 20. The statements with the highest weighted mean, suggesting time management as highly challenging is “There is difficulty in maximizing time for lesson discussion and activity” (3.55).
 21. The variables (age and sex, civil status, years of teaching in multi-grade classes, number of learners handled, relevant in-service trainings, attitude toward multi-grade classes) showed moderate to very weak associations with challenges encountered by teacher-respondents in handling multi-grade classes, and their correlations were determined to be not statistically significant. Only one variable has a significant correlation with teachers’ challenges encountered: grade level handled.
 22. The coping mechanisms employed by the teachers in handling multi-grade classes and the challenges encountered showed a moderate correlation. Also, their correlations were determined to be statistically significant. Thus, this indicates that the type of coping mechanism and strategy employed by the

teacher-respondents were relatively affected by the challenges encountered while handling multi-grade classes.

23. There was a strong desire for professional development opportunities, such as trainings, due to the reported less frequent national and regional training of the teacher respondents.

24. There was a strong encouragement to follow the principle of providing classroom discussion and activity, starting from an easy level and going to a more complex one, as the teachers revealed that it provides more effective learning.

Relationship Between the Coping Mechanism Employed by the Teachers in Handling Multi-Grade Classes and Their Challenges Encountered

The study found a significant connection between the challenges teachers face in multi-grade classrooms and the coping strategies they use. Researcher started with the assumption that no such relationship existed (null hypothesis). However, the analysis (p-value of 0.005, lower than the significance level of 0.05) showed strong evidence to reject this assumption.

Table 1

Relationship Between the Coping Strategies employed in Handling Multi-Grade Classes and Their Challenges Encountered

Indicator	Association		Chi-square Value	p-Value @ $\alpha=.05$	Evaluation/ Decision
	Correlation	Degree			
Coping Strategies Employed in Handling Multi-grade classes and their Challenges Encountered	.267	Moderate	0.000	0.005	S / Reject Ho.

$\omega=p<.001<.05$ pairwise normality deviated from the norm

S = Significant
NS = Not Significant

Additionally, a moderate correlation was identified. This means teachers likely adjust their coping mechanisms based on the specific difficulties they encounter. For

example, a teacher struggling with assessments for multiple grade levels might adopt a coping strategy focused on creating differentiated assessments. Recognizing this link between challenges and coping mechanisms allows schools and professional development programs to offer more targeted support. Training on specific coping mechanisms could be combined with training on how to address common challenges in multi-grade settings. Ultimately, this finding emphasizes the importance of acknowledging these challenges and equipping teachers with the resources and strategies to effectively manage them.

Conclusions

This study investigated the experiences of teachers handling multi-grade classes. The findings reveal a profile of the teachers and the challenges they encounter, along with the coping mechanisms they employ.

1. The majority of teachers are young (27-31 years old) and female.
2. Most teachers have a Master's Degree and some experience teaching multi-grade classes.
3. There's a split between newer teachers and those with longer tenure, with a gap in the 16–20-year experience range.
4. Teachers reported a generally positive attitude towards multi-grade classes.
5. Common challenges included crafting assessments, managing a noisy environment, and a lack of relevant training on multi-grade teaching.
6. Teachers frequently used coping mechanisms like grouping students, planning lessons in advance, and differentiating instruction based on learning styles.
7. There was a weak but significant correlation between teachers' educational attainment, positive attitude, and the number of coping mechanisms they used.
8. The challenges faced by teachers significantly influence the coping mechanisms they adopt.
9. Schools and professional development programs can better support teachers by providing training on multi-grade specific strategies and addressing resource limitations.
10. A positive attitude towards multi-grade classes appears to be beneficial.
11. Invest in professional development focused on multi-grade teaching methods.

Recommendations

This study provides valuable insights into the experiences of teachers handling multi-grade classes. Here are some recommendations based on the findings:

1. **Develop coping mechanisms:** The study highlights the importance of using various coping mechanisms to manage multi-grade classrooms. Teachers should continue to explore and develop these strategies, particularly in areas like curriculum management, classroom management, and time management.
2. **Seek professional development:** Teachers with higher educational attainment and those who attended relevant in-service training reported utilizing more coping mechanisms. This suggests that professional development opportunities can be beneficial. Schools and districts should prioritize providing training on multi-grade teaching strategies.
3. **Maintain a positive attitude:** A positive attitude towards multi-grade classes correlated with using more coping mechanisms. Teachers who see the value in multi-grade teaching are likely to be more proactive in finding solutions to challenges.
4. **Support teachers:** Many challenges were reported, particularly regarding a lack of resources and training. Schools and districts should find ways to support teachers by providing adequate learning materials, equipment, and access to technology. Additionally, they should prioritize offering training programs specifically focused on multi-grade teaching methods.
5. **Invest in professional development:** The desire for more professional development opportunities was strong. Schools and districts should offer more frequent in-service training on multi-grade teaching, and advocate for participation in national and regional training programs.
6. **The study suggests a youthful and predominantly female teaching force in this sample.** This may be a factor to consider when designing professional development programs.
7. **While the majority of teachers reported a positive attitude towards multi-grade classes, there is still room for improvement.** Schools and districts can explore ways to foster a more positive view of multi-grade teaching through mentorship programs or sharing success stories.

By implementing these recommendations, schools and districts can better support teachers in multi-grade settings, ultimately leading to a more positive and effective learning environment for students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research was conducted following ethical guidelines. This included getting approval beforehand, clearly explaining the study's purpose to participants (both in writing and verbally), and emphasizing their right to withdraw at any point without needing to explain their decision. Additionally, confidentiality of the participants' information was guaranteed.

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